

Research

Port led-development in Developing Countries for Effective and Efficient Maritime Transportation

Rakibul Hasan^{1*}, Kazi Mohiuddin², Prof. Wei Liu³

¹Master, School of Transportation, Shanghai Maritime University, Shanghai, China; 200135; PH (86) 18816533215; (Email: rakibulhasan1405@gmail.com)

²Ph.D., Candidate, School of Transportation, Shanghai Maritime University, Shanghai, China; 200135; PH (86) 15905843045; (Email: kazi.mohiuddin@yahoo.com)

³Ph.D., Professor, School of Transportation, Shanghai Maritime University, Shanghai, China; 200135; PH (86) 21-58855200Ext.2501; FAX (86) 21-38760201; (Email: weiliu@shmtu.edu.cn)

***Corresponding author**

Accepted: 20 October, 2020 ; Online: 27 October, 2020

DOI : <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4144746>

Abstract: Efficient port infrastructure and the strong maritime logistics sector have a significant contribution to economic growth. Coastal and domestic waterway shipping with the concept of port-led development is eco-friendly, energy-efficient, and minimizing domestic freight costs. Therefore, the river network and coastline of the developing countries keeping unutilized increasing the logistic cost and decrease the competitiveness compared to other developed countries. This study is qualitative research, and secondary data have been used. The data have been collected from different publications, journals, articles, related books, newspapers, annual reports of affiliated organizations etc. Collected data have been analyzed by strategic tools to find out the challenges and formulate the strategies for port-led development. In this work, several ports led development projects. Some port development models have been studied and tried to demonstrate how port-led development can show economic development in GDP growth. Some barriers to port-led development have been identified. Besides, sustainable port-led development in Bangladesh has been shown based on Shagarmala port-led development project. It has been found that draft limitation, hinterland connectivity, coastal community development, and industrial development are significant challenges for the port-led development of Chittagong Port. In this paper, long-term port-led development strategies and trade facilitation have been recommended to reduce the logistic cost for creating an internal and global competitive advantage compared to other exporting countries.

Keywords: Port-led development, Economic growth, Industrialization, port, Connectivity.

Introduction

Port led development in maritime economics is a crucial facet in the development of South Asia (SA). This region is mainly thriving in marine resources. India, Myanmar, Singapore, Malaysia, Indonesia, Bangladesh, and also Thailand all have coasts and also essential ports. This region's functions encourage the growth of interconnected maritime markets such as fishery, cargo handling, maritime transport, offshore oiling, etc. This area uses a wide variety of sources, from labor to oil gets. Slowly South Asian is becoming a central area in worldwide economics. Caldeirinha (2009) accomplished research to locate the connection between port growth and economic development. He showed the relevance of port as significant facilities assistance for economic development and additionally distinguished that ports are created for the development of the national development as they are prepared earlier to sustain the future demands infrastructure. According to the study, ports are divided into several categories like as different regional ports, global pivot, load facility, small ports etc. types such as load facility, international pivot, local ports, remote ports and so on. Likewise found that worldwide profession straight influences port growth.

The area was formerly identified as a substantial agricultural market. However, it is changing to the production field. According to Foreign Direct Investment (FDI), the SA economic situation is adjusting to the production and manufacturing industry, mainly due to the wealth of affordable human resources in the region. The progressive change to a manufacture-based economy from an agriculture-based economic situation has boosted the necessity of significant ports. This need for ports to establish is growing as an increasing number of FDI flow into the production market. Understandably, these ports in establishing nations have to maintain to provide to the demands of the production market. It's very crucial to develop the ports in SA to draw in potential FDI as well as national economic development in this region. Bangladesh, as a developing country in this region it is crucially important to develop their port to catch this opportunity and this port-led development take vital contribution in national up to the owing economy.

According to Modest (1999), the privatization of the port has increased the efficiency in Tanzania. The study has shown the effectiveness of privatization procedure and enterprise. To accomplishing the performance, a developed investment code, infrastructure, flexible labor market, capital market and efficient supervisory is very crucial. The significant growth of the economy in SA is experiencing the development of maritime economy in the area and the demand for maritime transportation is increasing which is the only method to move goods from one place to another as the region is surrendered with island and shorelines. On the other hand, in maritime transport, the primary traffic remains in ports which is a critical issue for port efficiency. Therefore, this study concentrates on the ports in SA especially at Chittagong port in Bangladesh.

Ports are considerably based on the development and growth of a country and economic situation. Some of the SEA countries have a better position, while others don't have the same development opportunities. For example, Singapore is located in the same region and Cambodia, but the economic development of both nations differs significantly. As a result of this distinction, the ports in the SEA also vary in dimension and kind. This paper in the middle of to locate a relation between port-led development and even financial growth and also exactly how essential a port leads country economic climate. Finally, the study offers a strategic and sustainable means to create a medium-size port based upon the effect they have on local economic advancement.

The prime minister of Bangladesh, Sheikh Hasina, initiated the vision 2021 right into concept 2041 to make long-term planning with the political election manifest as "Bangladesh marching ahead." According to the report of the World Bank, the GDP growth in Bangladesh is 7.2% in

2018 Bangladesh is listed in the Goldman Sachs which is listed in "Following 11". It is anticipated that GDP growth will be 7.1% in the 21st century. In Bangladesh, Foreign trade represents the ports execute 38% of the country's GDP and 87% of the countries' professions. The Port of Chittagong which is the principal port of the country, is considered as the heart of Bangladesh's economy (Goldman Sachs, 2007).

During the fiscal year, the 2017-2018 port of Chittagong handled over 2.7 million TEU containerized freight. The port observed 9% of container traffic growth recently against the countries' expected 7.1% GDP growth and also anticipated to be surpassed up by 2020. The government is currently preparing to construct a new seaport in the southwestern part of the country and a deep-sea port off the coast of Chittagong to balance the growth of trade in the country.

Bangladesh stands on the second-most textile exporting industry globally, and Bangladesh Government has set the target to \$50 billion per year by 2021 but seriously lacks enough maritime infrastructures. Development in traffic via ports would be led by oil refineries, where primary gamers intend to increase their existing refining capacity by the year 2025. Garments and textiles, Iron-ore, consumer, automobiles, and electronics would also share enormous growth in merchandise trade in the upcoming years. That's why port-led development vital important in this region particularly Bangladesh. For this consequence, the port plays a crucial role in driving the country's economy and emerge some problems for port development in Bangladesh. As a result, this study has been formed in the following research problems.

Ports make nearly 90% of the complete worldwide trade volume in Bangladesh. With the Federal government of Bangladesh's "Make in Bangladesh" initiative for fast economic development, it is estimated that the share of merchandise trade in Bangladesh's GDP would increase substantially in the following five years. Presently, the percentage of product trade-in Gross Domestic Product (GDP) of Bangladesh is 7.2 and also USD 227.9 billion in value terms (as per World Bank- 2018) compared to 7.1 or USD 623 billion worth of merchandise trade of India. This data recommends the substantial possibility for development in merchandise sell Bangladesh in the years ahead, which would undoubtedly demand technical progression and capability renovation of ports. Indian Ocean region is significant as virtually 50% of the global trade, as well as about 60% of the worldwide oil website traffic, passes through this area. Bangladeshi ports can play a crucial role by giving technological in addition to infrastructural support to these vessels.

Port led Development According to Back Admiral M Khaled Iqbal Port led growth implies a port-led model of economic advancement that comprises ports unique economic zones, SEZs rail roadway air as well as river connection with the hinterland The vision of port-led promotion is to lower logistics set you back for both domestic and also export-import cargo with very little framework financial investment In this the concept of port-led advancement is a tactical and customer-oriented effort to improve ports to ensure that port-led development can be augmented and also coasts can be established to add to national financial growth. It looks in the direction of upgrading the existing ports into modern-day world-class docks and integrates the success of the ports as well. Industrial concentrations and hinterland and reliable discharge networks by inland highway railways and tidal rivers, resulting in the financial action of coastal communities being powered by ports. Activities of SEZ needs to be ensured a comparative study followed by two corresponding case studies shows the port-led advancement on economic climates of 2 gigantic rising economic power of Asia.

Literature review

This literature review accords with the research study title, depict a theoretical introduction as well as articulate the appropriate literature which remains in line with the research questions of this research study. This literature evaluation pulls the researcher in the direction of the research trouble he attended to. This evaluation of literary works boosts the reasoning of the research study by discovering the hidden truths from the previous research studies. It additionally gives the scientist quickly to improve his very own research study by attending to the links and also spaces of those pertinent studies. Formerly, to study both the factors that impact financial growth and the elements that influence port-led production, various research has been carried out. A few of the existing literary works important for this study will undoubtedly be reviewed in this component.

In 2015, there are a few scientific types of research has been carried out on this subject. According to the study of Tongzon (1995), Tongzon & Heng (2005), and Loo & Hook (2002), there are a few factors of port performance as well as port effectiveness. The ports perform an essential function in the growth and advancement of economic climates on the neighborhood, regional and national degrees (Li-zhuo, 2012; Deng, Lu, & Xiao, 2013). Following Li-zhuo (2012) suggestion, the price, as well as the efficiency of the production field, has a significant influence on the development of port logistics. It can be described by the fact that improved port logistics support to minimize the transportation expenses in the manufacturing market and also rise performance which impacts economic growth and development. Li-zhuo (2012) defines the multiple effects on the development of logistics performance. For example, the national income rises several times as a consequence of the investment in port logistics due to the demand for aspects of manufacturing, products and also brand-new innovations and also equipment will undoubtedly be boosted. To evaluate this argumentation, experimental research was carried out from 1995 to 2010 for the Qinhuangdao port in China by Li-zhuo (2012). The (GDP) of Qinhuangdao was utilized as a variable of economic growth at the time of the port logistics and was measured indirectly by the throughput of the products. By the way, the study took a look at the interconnection between GDP and port throughput. The outcomes presented that the throughput growth and port logistics or impacts on the rise of GDP. However, the effect of GDP in port logistics or throughput was tiny and not considerable and the port-led growth effect is not discussed.

Ports were the subject of Langen (2004) and Langen & Chouly (2004) as economic collections. The effect of port competence on the economic development of a nation or country was explored by numerous other researchers (Bottasso, Conti, Ferrari, Merk & Tei, 2013). These and other empirical findings will be revamped and also used as a theoretical basis for the experimental portion of this research paper in the literary work testimonial. Most of the investigations are not current and too focused on ports in the Middle East or worldwide, or UNESCAP accomplished numerous studies to identify ports. Most of the elements used to improve port competence are focused on trans-shipment, which focuses on trans-shipment since the best way to create ports is to gain trans-shipment cargo throughput (MPPM, 2006). An analysis undertaken by Notteboom is another survey that determines the term 'tons center'; his report distinguishes the European container port infrastructure based on their willingness to achieve the status of 'load center.' Notteboom uses Hayuth's lots center concept, as a result of the intermodal transport networks and containerization, he identifies them as large ports with a large cargo concentration (Hayuth Y 1982) (Notteboom, 1997).

The effect of port competence and productivity on Bangladesh's financial development was addressed in Begum (2003). The author took as an example of the port of Chittagong for research. The writer revealed that port economics, macroeconomics and port efficiency are related. Because

the economic condition in Bangladesh and also the maritime reliance of nations is growing, the task and importance of the port of Chittagong are growing. Bangladesh's economic climate, SWOT evaluation is done to reveal the weak point and toughness of the port authority in your area. Within the room, a relative assessment is performed to examine the port competition. In this situation, both short-term and long-term planning is advised to boost the current situation.

Jansen (2014) attempted to anticipate container freight throughput in ports utilizing numerous versions and situations. The function of the thesis was to figure out the many aspects that affect projecting container throughput. Research says that there are three vital fundamentals to be identified whereas estimating container throughput precisely proper evaluation of port competitors and GDP growth in the region. However, various components cannot be evaluated with the aid of a qualitative approach. For eg, shipping lines can have an effect on the market share of the port, which cannot be expected.

Brox (2014) examined the port of Valencia that shows the necessity of competitive ports for regional financial growth. Ports are revealed in research as a catalyst for international economic development. According to this qualitative analysis, it has been found that the port of Valencia, as well as its hinterlands, has an excellent perspective of being an engine for regional financial development. However, there are some future difficulties have also been mentioned.

Chai (2005) researched the economic growth of port payments in his geographical region, where he used Kenyan ports as a case study. The author discussed the historical history of the ports and the maritime burden on the world sector, the traditional port model and also the port assessment, the overview of the economic situation in Kenya, the importance of the Kenyan ports, the SWOT assessment of the Kenyan ports, the expectation of financial growth and the prediction of containers. After that, the port identified required centers to accommodate potential demand and offered a few remedies and suggestions.

In 2013, the OECD published a series of analyses of the positive and detrimental effects of ports in their respective cities on separate port cities (Merk, 2013). Their outcome was that ports act between local ports, hinterlands, and the rest of the world as a trade organizer for the regional economic situation. The regional economy obtains a connection to the international market by ports that increase exports and imports and thereby reduce transport costs. By engaging innovative manufacturing activities, adding capital, changing awareness, ports enable local economies to be extra-affordable globally. In general, across the linked hinterland, ports have had an apparent positive effect. The level of these consequences, however, varies with the existence of actions. In the regional economy, exports and imports create more inclusive value than transshipment operations.

In addition, many other activities are also carried out by ports, such as ferries, fishing, traveling, or other social gatherings (Rodrigue, 2013). The port still has a beneficial impact on the job sector, which generates direct scope of tasks for the area community. Even it has decreased with the technological progress of a variety of jobs. It's coming to be much more outstanding extensive. Just a couple of thousand tasks are suited in a big port nowadays.

This area will check out patterns in the released literary works on port development and also associated concerns emerging from those trends towards present advancements in a port. The advancement of port approaches, regionalization, decriminalization, and growth of the port system is the general ideas that are also stated in most of the port logistics literature and will be discussed in the discussion. The literary works evaluation will undoubtedly develop the basis for a new development technique.

The port growth as a research study effort that got attention with the UNCTAD2 appointing of a study into how ports have established traditions and level of maturity of ports. According to the UNCTAD study in the 1990s, it showed that ports had changed from a type of procedure focused on landlords to far more organized operations. The model sector of UNCTAD is divided into three separate groups, reflecting a development period. No logistic intervention by the port is seen in the first generation. In contrast, the second generation contains some logistic relations, and ports act as logistic integrators in the third generation. There is an activity within these generations that indicates a growth in the skills needed to identify UNCTAD 's three-generation port model as a more mature port structure. It is focused on the historical development of the major global ports. It is also an attempt to illustrate how reduced-generation ports can be set up in gradual measures. The layout is very focused on how the port is connected to the movement of freight and also shows that ports need to concentrate on assisting in the processing of integrated shipment.

The UNCTAD model was later adhered to by the WORK PORT model by Ninipoulos et al. (2000), which resulted from a project moneyed by the EU commission. The WORK PORT version is based upon a research study job exploring how brand-new developing technologies and other exterior developments have played a role in developing ports. Among the WORK PORT project's final thoughts was that the three-stage generation version of UNCTAD was too rigid in its approach to explaining the real growth of ports. One more verdict was that the port could be at different stages of development in other locations simultaneously.

Later on, Beresford et al. (2004) assess the UNCTAD model and the WORK PORT design. They additionally end that the UNCTAD model is too rigid and that port development is usually a lot more distributed between various locations. This is likewise validated by an extra standard consider as ports have systems that are highly established, and also some that are not. Moreover, the argument is made to switch from one age to another, but in a different constant way, the refrain is from making hops.

The models are based on the literature on port development. Specifically, the constant advancement defined in the WORK PORT design, as well as the review by Beresford et al. (2004), stands for the historic port's development and also the enhancing focus on a different integrated technique to port growth. The advancements have revealed that it is necessary to consider at the hinterland and foreland during determining on a tactical approach. Figure-1 shows precisely how the WORK PORT design determines the development of various areas of the port's operations. The growing arrowhead indicates that this area is a raised focus or effect. The arrowhead can likewise be tightening, e.g., environmental impact, suggesting that e.g. the environmental footprint diminishes. In relation to this paper, the intriguing aspect of this version is that it can be used to define the technique for enhanced logistic involvement in the hinterland.

Figure-1: Increasing integration of ports into the supply chain (Pettit and Beresford, 2009).

A lot of the designs and also the research study literary works associated with port development. The research performed was focused on case studies of ports of a more massive scale, such as Rotterdam and Antwerp. In using different methods with narrower ports, several problems are found. There is a need for an updated approach that recognizes that smaller ports involve extra cautious involvement in creating the numerous supply chains of firms and even participation in the hinterland of the port, i.e., to focus on particular goods or objects types to identify methods of intervention. To determine which item types to focus on, an approach could explore which products are qualified for a strategic push from a port.

Regionalization – Specialize, expand and organize into the region

The regionalization is the activity in which a port becomes an important transport center for an entire region, such as, for example, Hamburg and Rotterdam. Nevertheless, regionalization often looks for smaller ports to decide if the progress of the hinterland and the running of the port will be influenced to stimulate greater demand for the goods provided by the port. In this figure-2: Notteboom and also Rodrigue (2005) review a few of the obstacles commonly present in this advancement such as governance concerns, capital raising, as well as the control and collaboration that is needed, in-between companions. To produce a successful regionalization approach, it is required to improve the atmosphere in the ports based upon the challenges or obstacles (Notteboom and Rodrigue, 2005).

Figure-2: Illustrates regionalization, which is defined as the gradual expansion of the geographical influence of a port (Notteboom and Rodrigue, 2005)

Research Design or Methodology

This paper generates an academic history based upon a literary works review to demonstrate that there is a partnership between port-led growth as well as economic advancement and additionally produce initial presumptions on the connection between port-led development and also financial gain. These hypotheses will undoubtedly be evaluated quantitatively to show the relationship between port-led growth and economic development of the region. Afterward, an empirical study was conducted to find the barrier to lasting change among the various stakeholders and represent their reaction. It showed a sustainable method to attain a port led-development. The progression of the sustainable port led-development is gauged by the respondent feedback and literary works testimonial. The research approach demonstrated what the activity of the research study is, just how to continue, precisely how to assess progress, as well as what makes up success (Perez, 2008). This research study is complied with by the second research study method and integrated by the qualitative methods of primary research as well as literary works evaluation methods of an additional research study where information extracted from both the primary and also different sources.

Analysis

The use of this paper as a symbol of financial growth is GDP, which can be differentiated as the cumulative amount of all goods and also as a solution established within a country's boundaries within a year. This diverse aspect is that, regardless of who makes them, GDP contains every sort of products and services produced within limits. The restriction of GDP to the territorial boundaries of a nation is another unique feature. GDP just cares about the importance of goods and services created within a country as well. The money that the nation's inhabitants produce beyond the national territories is left out. While, for the sake of evidence, there are several forms of GDP figures, such as current GDP, small GDP, and actual GDP, this paper uses real GDP.

The aim of the analysis is to make use of GDP because of the specific efficiency of GDP in calculating the economic growth of countries. If GDP estimates the total value of all products and solutions produced within a nation's borders, given that this paper aims to analyze the relationship, it needs to integrate the principle of source endowment. This definition, also known as the Heckscher-Ohlin definition, states that in a particular region, services are allocated accordingly, making worldwide exchange possible depending on resource difference (Stopford, 2007). GDP fits the principle in accordance with this definition, the idea of space or position containment relative to root history.

An additional explanation that GDP is an acceptable growth achievement for this research is that the career is included in GDP. GDP covers domestic intake, government spending, capital activity, and foreign trade, as indicated by the assumption of a gross value of exports with a gross value of imports.

According to the mathematical equation, the GDP could be composed:

$$\text{GDP} = C + I + G + (X - M).$$

(Anon., n.d.) GDP= Gross Domestic Product. C = Household consumption that includes any kind of expense on products and services that a household invests in sustaining itself, other than housing.

I= Investment consists of every financial investment made by family or organization in products and also services, consisting of structure, insurance coverage, as well as tools.

G= Government Cost covers any spending on goods or technologies made by the government.

X= Gross Export, which comprises all products and solutions manufactured for the use of numerous other nations.

M= Gross Import, consisting of each commodity and solution imported from abroad as well. This vector is deductive as it reflects the discharge of funds from one country to another and prevents being treated as residential development.

According to the study, the GDP has a straight partnership with the port because it integrated international trade in its estimation. In the global profession, represented by X and M, items are probably to be moved to utilize seaborne transport with the specific port. This is primarily the case in Southeast Asia, where marine transport is used to transport nearly all trade worldwide. The relation between GDP and the port is evident in the feeling that there would be a shift in GDP as well as the need for port solutions if there is a change in global trade. This sense of port facilities conditions denoted by X and M that are partly otherwise entirely dependent on foreign trade (Rees, 1971) is called derived need. In the following section of this segment, the relation between GDP, exports and the derived demand for port services will be further addressed.

Formerly, the procedure showed the cause of why GDP is one of the most appropriate signs for a country's economic advancement. The region is committed to explaining the relationship between

GDP and the subsequent port service demand as well. Second, port service is a means to an end that implies that individuals do not need a port solution for the service to be accessed. It is a way to a future that in many cases, to supply items from one location to one more for a higher financial worth. For that purpose, the demand for the port service is extracted from the competition for the actual goods being shipped. The consequent requirement is called this form of need, which arises from demand for other resources or goods.

The need for port facilities stems from the demand for a service from one location which, at a greater financial gain, needs to be transported to other locations. The obligation to sell a service from one location to another is strengthened by the variable endowment theory, which simply discusses roots that are different from one location to another. This term further distinguishes foreign trading when one nation needs capital to create products from an adjacent region.

The more a government makes, the higher the market for primary content, as well as the more goods generated, in comparison to EOI. Extra raw materials and other products are demanded by the worldwide market by foreign trade and further port solutions are needed. It can be claimed, combined with the outcome of the former zone, that the acquired demand for port facilities increases as a nation's GDP increases. According to the understanding of Martin Stopford in his book *The Financial Principles of the Maritime Career*, the relation between the growth of GDP and the consequent need for the production of port facilities can be addressed on three grounds: greater economic conditions provide a higher demand for the required materials and products transported by sea. With financial growth, the high GNP diminishes regional wealth, and a nation can pay in return for imports and more exports.

GDP and International Trade Linkages

GDP plays a crucial role in this research, which is considered as the landmark of national economic growth. The reason why GDP is used as opposed to GNP has been explained in the previous area of this chapter. This aims to describe precisely how GDP and the International profession that stood for by exports as well as imports belong and also what relation do, they have. According to the formula, suggestions prove that international trade has substantial significance to GDP. Cambodia and postcolonialism Vietnam who are the state-led economic nations, the procedure does not essentially show the GDP mix. Moreover, these nations are seldom entailed if not out-of-the-way from global trade. Particularly, market-led economic climates countries such as Singapore, Malaysia and Indonesia, which are included proactively in the global profession. Hence, the formula is capable of replicating its GDP mix. Additionally, in countries that have a market-led advancement path, EOI has made worldwide trade as unavoidably an essential and also massive part of the GDP mix with industrialism. According to a report, in 2015, the world seaborne career exceeded 10 billion tons and also grew by 2.1 percent relative to the previous year. Conversely, in 2015, global GDP growth rose by 2.5 percent. It is obvious, according to historical evidence, that the world seaborne profession has a very favorable relationship with world GDP growth. The throughput of containers is almost double that of GDP growth. (2016, UNCTD). Figure-3: demonstrates that the world maritime sector is inter-related with the growth of world GDP. If the maritime career is an optimistic development, the growth of world GDP would also be favorable.

GDP and Chittagong port linkage:

Figure-3: GDP concerning total container handling annually
Source: Chittagong port authority on 25 March 2018

Figure-4: Our GDP growth with the total cargo handling in a ton in CP
Source: Chittagong port authority on 25 March 2018

The cargo, as well as container managing the growth of Bangladesh, are significantly associated with GDP development. Based upon that the cargo and container handling estimate based on a critical plan of the attack made by the expert Hamburg Port Consulting (HPC) for Chittagong Port is shown this number suggests that different types of freight need each day is raising and also we see that nearly 50% freight is dry mass as well as fluid bulk that means we need more center for dry size and liquid bulk.

Figure-4: Demand of different types of cargo in Chittagong port.

Source: Data source HPC 2016

Figure-5: Container demand forecast in Chittagong port up to 2043

The total number of container demand at Certified Public Accountant will undoubtedly be 2.9 million TEUs. It is predicted that it will still be 5.6 million TEUs in 2036 and will steadily decrease to 5.0 million TEUs by which time from 2036 the deep-sea port will work. The deep-water port will definitely take care of 50 percent of the container 's nearly 5.1 million TEUs at the same time in 2043 (Bandar Barta,2016).

Strategic way to sustainable port-led development in Chittagong port:

Industrialization positively impacts per capita income as well as, for this reason, the success of the area. Nonetheless, for automation to be competitive, it requires to have effective and also efficient logistics. Proximity and sufficient affiliations to ports are essential factors market to be affordable. The possibility of seeking port-led advancement is enormous in Bangladesh, as apparent from a relative evaluation with India's shagarmala port-led growth. According to Shagarmala job, the four indications of port-led development and also this paper discovers a lasting port-led advancement in the port of Chittagong based upon shagarmala assignment. This number indicates that these four columns currently exist in Bangladesh yet they have some constraint and the author search for this barrier and also together this fore variable led the economic climate to create the nation.

Figure-7: A way for sustainable port-led development in Chittagong port according to shagarmala project.

Source: Author creation

Summary of the respondent’s response of administrative questionnaire:

By empirical survey in this paper demonstrated that there is some significant barrier to reach the lasting port-led advancement that is shown on the table-1. There are lots of elements affecting the growth of the port yet in the context of developing nations like Bangladesh, and this problem is a significant issue to reach sustainable port-led advancement such as hinterland connection,

framework growth, area advancement, industrialization as well as EEZ. This survey was carried out among the maritime professional, port authority, shipping company, all stakeholders and also provide their response according to the questioner as well as attempted to develop a method to attain a lasting development in creating region.

Giving appropriate connectivity to ports is an obstacle in Bangladesh. The main difficulties to port connection are under-leveraging of residential waterways; seriously constricted rail framework along with introductory courses, sub-optimal modal mix for container products, combining of city web traffic with port traffic, absence of a collaborated end to finish preparation for mass logistics and also constrained last-mile-connectivity in between ports as well as vital industrial hinterlands. Bangladesh's hinterland connection is generally based upon roadway as well as rail network with residential waterways, both coastal shipping as well as inland routes playing a minimal role. We need to plan excellent connectivity between the ports as well as the hinterland.

Ser	Administrative propositions	Respondent's Response					Remarks
		SA	A	NU	DA	SDA	
1.	Limitation of land is one of the significant barriers to develop port infrastructure	105	15	10	15	5	70% SA
2.	Limitation of adequate depth for entering larger vessel in Chittagong port is a potential barrier for further expansion	91	31	17	8	3	61% SA
3	To meet the present demand, Chittagong port has limited cargo handling equipment and jetties	71	41	15	21	5	47 SA & 31% A
4	Siltation is a critical problem for inland connectivity in Bangladesh.	74	30	18	21	9	49% SA& 20% A
5	Difficult to shift logistic chin from Road transport to inland transport	60	30	23	20	18	40%SA& 20% A
6	Shortage of skillful employee involvement for port operation and port management	107	21	15	7	2	71% SA
7	Fishermen in the coastal area and local community are so far away from	62	64	15	7	2	43%A & 41% SA
8	Island in coastal area are not developed in concept of port led development	79	53	15	7	6	46% SA& 35% A
9	Location of industrial area is not suitable position to use the Chittagong port.	74	30	18	21	9	49%SA & 20 A
10	According to Chittagong port high potential are mark for port led development	23	29	7	63	39	41%DA& 26% SDA
11	Special Economic Zone and coastal economic zone is not indicated properly in the concept of port-led development	54	36	14	30	17	36% SA & 24% A

Bangladesh is a big possible nation having with a strategic area in South East Asia, colossal human resources, abundant land, and also rivers. The Bay of Bengal also bounds it to the south with a 710km standard which can be considered as the gateway to the entire world. The country has been keeping a specific GDP growth pattern of 6.2% over the last decade even amongst common all-natural calamities and political turmoil. The government is experiencing an expected 9.2 percent growth in sea-borne trade per year. The experts are anticipating that by 2020 the country's overall annual seaborne business will remain in the series of 70 to 80 million tones. It is not feasible for Chittagong Port and also Mongla Port to birth this mass trade quantity even if the ports are more developed. Therefore, the port will have to be functional in full swing by 2020. RMG sector is adding to making more than 25 billion bucks which are 80 percent of earning from the export of Bangladesh. This field is anticipating to make 50 billion by the 50th Anniversary of Bangladesh in 2021. So, it is clear that the economic situation in Bangladesh is growing. To provide even more paces to this development port framework both inability as well as number is to be strengthened. The nation's central seaside zone is additionally demanding an expansion of the country's port facilities.

In order to be more effective and to remain a powerful port, the Port Authority must implement the requisite changes and strengthen its organizational and administrative processes in the future. Reforms may be fleeting or long-term. The following problems should be discussed as part of the short-term overhaul of the following concepts.

- a. To improve operational efficiency, it is required to strengthen human resources efficiency by utilizing work hours and training.
- b. A recruitment procedure should be simplified and unoccupied posts must be full of young and energetic human resources. A decrease of over-aged labor needs to be considered.
- c. The chain of command must be shortened, and the specific division needs to have the ability to manage the new decision-making relating to preparation as well as development activities.
- d. Political influence ought to be gotten rid of by the Certified Public Accountant.
- e. The department related to planning should be efficient and workers need to be available with functional, engineering, economics and also data understanding. These will certainly increase the ability of the planning division.
- f. The institutions related to Training must be well geared up as well as well arranged.
- g. Various welfare tasks need to be placed for an excellent working society within the CPA organization.
- h. The port authority should be provided with the maximum feasible authority for operating, managing, recruiting, creating, critical preparation as well as carrying out a plan of attack. This will choose simplifying and also Certified Public Accountants will have the ability to take the essential choice without any delay.
- I. CPA needs to adhere to a property owner work model for port handling and includes more private enterprises for port operation. Furthermost, CPA needs to alter from its authority type strategy to trade facilitator. Interactions of the inter-department needs to be enhanced. For taking a new name might, there should have a great choice to alter the port method towards trade assistance.

Figure-8: Author creation

Conclusion

There is a significant connection between logistics efficiency as well as worldwide professional competitiveness and also the organization can be evaluated and also anticipated. Regardless of Bangladesh's astounding profession and maritime potential in the Main Oriental sub-continent cluster, her logistics performance is being tormented by the port blockage, traffic congestion as well as difficult inland transport, emerging from the inadequate state of facilities, insufficient handling equipment, personalized administration as well as documentation delays, the diversity of national government firms running at the port, and also the absence of trained and certified logistics workers. It is believed that while maintaining ongoing nationwide infrastructural upgrade establishing different transport frameworks, along with extensive profession assistance and a logistics approach that includes trade-enabling policies, processes and treatments can and also will remedy the scenario, as they will certainly make the country more attractive, budget-friendly as well as competitive for trade. Significantly, the Sonadia is discovered to be the 'ideal' place with the lowest logistics cost to website a new port that will satisfy the trade assistance need for Bangladesh's global trade competitiveness. The study likewise noted that this area might work as either a seaport, dry port or logistics facility. The security problem should be taken on with all severity to recover the self-confidence of international capitalists, some of which are already divesting away from Bangladesh to close-by India, Myanmar, Srilanka, as well as Pakistan. It is likewise thought that the incorporation of useful framework maritime logistics, as well as supply chain programs in the tertiary education and learning curriculum, will certainly address the problem of scarcity of requisite employees to meet the dynamic as well as ever-growing demand of Bangladesh's economic climate.

Therefore, according to the recognized benefits accruable from the adjustment of the recommended recommendations, Bangladesh stands to enhance productivity, draw in more cargo, boost earnings to the government, lower operating price, and lastly, increase its competition among the South Oriental cluster of nations.

Reference:

- [1] Bottasso, A., Conti, M., Ferrari, C., Merk, O., & Tei, A. (2013). *The impact of port throughput on local employment: Evidence from a panel of European regions*. *Transport Policy*, 27, 32-38. doi: 10.1016/j.add your text here. Times new roman 12 points. 1.5 space.
- [2] Begum, H. (2017). *Impact of port efficiency and productivity on the economy of Bangladesh- a case study of Chittagong port*.
- [3] Caldeirinha, V. R., Felício, J. A., & Coelho, J. (2009). *The influence of characterizing factors on port performance, measured*. *Recent Advances in Environment, Energy Systems and Naval Science*, 58- 71.
- [4] Chai, S. (2005) *Can ports contribute to the economic development of the regions they serve? An examination of the potential, if any, of using the Kenya Ports Authority as an engine for Kenya's economic recovery and development*
- [5] Kakusa, M. (1999) *Restructuring of the port industry in Tanzania: Privatization of the Tanzania Harbors Authority*
- [6] Loo, B. P., & Hook, B. (2002). *Interplay of international, national and local factors in shaping container port development: A case study of Hong Kong*. *Transport Reviews: A Transnational Transdisciplinary Journal*, 22(2), 219-245. doi:10.1080/01441640110091486
- [7] Li-zhuo, L. (2012). *Analysis of the Relationship Between QinHuangDao Port Logistics and Economic Growth*. *Advances in information Sciences and Service Sciences (AISS)*, 4(4), 105-114. doi: 10.4156/AISS.vol4.issue4.13
- [8] Langen, P. W. de, & Chouly, A. (2004). *Hinterland Access Regimes in Seaports*. *European Journal of Transport and Infrastructure Research (EJTIR)*, 4(4), 361-380. Retrieved from www.ejtir.tbm.tudelft.nl
- [9] Langen, P. W. de, & Chouly, A. (2004). *Hinterland Access Regimes in Seaports*. *European Journal of Transport and Infrastructure Research (EJTIR)*, 4(4)
- [10] Merk, O. (2013) “*The Competitiveness of Global Port-Cities: Synthesis Report*” OECD Regional Development Working Paper 2013/13, OECD publishing. Access date: 28 June 2017
- [11] Rear Admiral M. Khaled Iqbal (2018). “*Port led Development-A Key to the Economic Prosperity of Bangladesh*”
- [12] Rodrigue, J.P. (2013) “*The geography of transport systems*” Routledge, New York
- [13] Syafaaruddin (2009). *Evaluation of Container Terminal Efficiency Performance in Indonesia: Future Investment*
- [14] Stopford, M. (2007). *Maritime Economics*. New York, New York, United States of America: Routledge.
- [15] Tongzon, J. L. (1995). *Determinants of port performance and efficiency*. *Transportation Research Part A: Policy and Practice*, 29(3), 245-252. doi:10.1016/0965-8564(94)00032

Rakibul Hasan

School of Transportation, Shanghai Maritime University, Shanghai, China; 200135; PH (86) 18816533215; or +8801915955942 (Email: rakibulhasan1405@gmail.com)

Kazi Mohiuddin

School of Transportation, Shanghai Maritime University, Shanghai, China; 200135; (Email: kazi.mohiuddin@yahoo.com)

Acknowledgments

First of all, I would like to thank the Almighty Allah for giving me His grace and mental strength to accomplish this paper. I should thank to Shanghai Maritime University authority for giving me an opportunity to work in a very relevant field with our subject and prepare this paper in a formal way as a part of our master degree. I would like to thank from the bottom of my heart to my supervisor Mr. Wie Liu, Professor, School of Transportation, Shanghai Maritime University, Shanghai, China for encouraging me to start this work with very interesting subject matter. Despite his busy schedule his regular supervision, guidance and dedicated supporting play an important role to accomplish paper.

Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

© 2020 by the authors. TWASP, NY, USA. Author/authors are fully responsible for the text, figure, data in above pages. This article is an open access article distributed under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>)

